

Emotional Intelligence, Socio - Emotional Competence and Human Capital

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 29 April 2021	The concept of emotional intelligence and emotional competency is contemporary issue in the management literature. Therefore, it has become imperative to study, understand and leverage it for the sake of enhancing the capacity of human capital at the level of individual as well as organizations. As the pace of change is fast and uncertain in the world of work, it is making more and more demands on a person's cognitive, emotional and physical resources. These set of capabilities are becoming progressively significant. It is because majority of the concerns in organization involve people in different roles. Hence, emotional intelligence must become a determining factor for their effective management. Emotional and personal competencies are inevitable to identify measure, predict and manage performance at workplace resulting in its effectiveness. Thereby, it boosts the worth of the human capital. That is the reason why, the competencies possessed by the people have a significant bearing on the extent to which they can actualize their emotional intelligence. The current paper sets out to examine the concept and correlation between the emotional intelligence, socio emotional competencies, emotionally intelligent behavior and human capital. The study recommends that
Corresponding Author: Dr. Jyotirmayee Choudhury	emotional intelligence is significantly related with the socio-emotional competencies which ultimately strengthen emotionally intelligent behavior to leverage human capital at individual and organizational level.
KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence, Socio-emotional Competencies, Emotionally Intelligent Behavior, Human Capital	

1. INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence is a sort of social intelligence emerged as a major psychological construct in the early 1990s. It was conceptualized as a set of abilities largely analogous to general intelligence. The concept emotional intelligence is defined as the self-perceived ability, capacity, skill or self to recognize, quantify and manage the emotions of one's self, of others. The theory is appreciating considerable backing in management literature and has had successful applications in many domains. James Dozier a U.S. Army brigadier general who was abducted by Italian terrorist group discovered the power of emotional intelligence in 1981 which saved his life. He found emotions as contagious. Therefore, a single person having emotional competency can influence the emotional tone of a group. By getting his own emotions under control, James Dozier remained calm and conveyed his coolness to his abductors through his behavior and activities. Subsequently his captors also captured his calmness and became more rational towards James Dozier. In retrospect, Dozier found that his capability to control his own emotional reactions stuck his abductors and

ultimately saved his life (Campbell, 1990). Dozier could able to perceive the emotional reactions of his abductors accurately. By regulating his own emotions and then expressing them successfully, he could able to manage the emotions of his captors. With this background the study is intended towards in depth analysis on the concept emotional intelligence, emotionally intelligent behaviour and its impact on leveraging Human Capital. The study uses emotional intelligence and emotional competency interchangeably as the concept emotional competencies are linked to and based on emotional intelligence although a certain level of emotional intelligence is necessary to learn the emotional competencies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mayer, Salovey, & Caruso (2000) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive emotion, integrate emotion in thought, comprehend and reason with emotion and ultimately regulate emotion in the self and others. Therefore, it has become imperative to comprehend and be conscious of the research and theory on which it is based. It is also important to study various dimensions of emotional

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intelligence to shape socio-emotional competencies which is central in leveraging human capital and subsequent work performance. Emotions provide valuable information about relationships, behavior and every aspect of the human life. The most recent research shows that emotions are productive to contribute to increase in performance and appropriate decision making both at job and in private life. According to Thorndike (1920), out of several intelligence human possess, social intelligence is that particular type of skill which comprehend and manage other people to progress prudently in human relations. **Human relations** are significant factor which contribute to workplace efficiency and efficacy. People with good supervisor- subordinate relations are four times less likely to quit the organization than those who have poor relationship (Zipkin, 2000).

Psychologists John Mayer and Peter Salovey familiarized the concept emotional intelligence in series of paper. According to them, emotions are inner state of mind that coordinate physiological responses, cognitions and conscious awareness.

David Wechsler in 1943 referred both non-intellective and intellective elements of intelligence. He described the effects of non-intellective factors on intelligent behavior. The non-intellective factors such as affective, personal and social factors are essential to foresee one's capability to flourish in life.

In 1983, Howard Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligences involved both Interpersonal intelligence and Intrapersonal intelligence. The capacity to know oneself, to value one's feelings, fears, worries and motivations is called intrapersonal intelligence. Interpersonal intelligence involves the capacity to realize the intentions, motivations and desires and needs of other people. In Gardner's view, Intelligent Quotient (IQ) do not explain cognitive ability fully. It also lacks the ability to explain performance outcomes completely.

According to Salovey and Mayer (1990), EI as the “the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions”. They

argued that individuals high in EI had certain emotional abilities and skills related to appraising and regulating emotions in the self and others. Therefore, it is claimed that individuals high in EI could accurately perceive and regulate certain emotions in themselves as well as others in order to attain a range of adaptive outcomes or emotional states such as motivation, creative thinking and positivism.

Mayer and Salovey (1993) confirm that being able to direct one's emotions, as well as being able to understand and influence other people's emotional responses, one can effectively adapt to an environment. They defined emotional intelligence as: “the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to distinguish among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking, behaviour and actions”. Goleman (1995) in his book “Emotional Intelligence” brought wide popular recognition to the concept of emotional intelligence.

Mayer and Salovey's 1997 model of EI concerns the “the ability of an individual to perceive, appraise and express emotions appropriately. Mayer and Salovey (1997) said that emotional intelligence constitutes “the ability to perceive emotions accurately, to access and generate emotions accordingly, assist thought, to understand emotions and organize emotional knowledge and to thoughtfully regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth”.

Bar-On (1997) defines emotional intelligence as being concerned with understanding successfully one's self and others, relating well to other's emotion and adapting to and coping with the immediate surroundings in order to be more effective and positive in dealing with environmental demands. Bar-On (1997) postulates that emotional intelligence matures over time. He clarified that it can be improved through training, programming and therapy. Later, Cherniss and Goleman (2001) claimed that emotional intelligence provides the foundation to recognize and regulate emotions in oneself and others.

Table 1. A Framework for Emotional Competencies (Cherniss & Goleman, 2001)

	Personal Competencies (intrapersonal)	Social Competencies (Interpersonal)
Recognition	Self-Awareness - Emotional self-awareness - Accurate self-assessment - Self-confidence - Own culture awareness	Social Awareness - Empathy - Service orientation - Organizational awareness - Other culture awareness
Regulation	Self-Management - Emotional self-control - Trustworthiness - Conscientiousness - Adaptability - Achievement drive Initiative	Social Skills - Developing others - Influence - Communication - Conflict management - Visionary leadership

	- Nonjudgmentalness	- Catalyzing change - Building bonds -Teamwork and collaboration Respect
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Goleman (2001b) has suggested EI may involve four higher order factors influencing each other. It includes: 1. the capacity to recognize emotions in the self i.e Self-Awareness); 2. the capacity to regulate emotions in the self i.e Self-Management); 3. the capacity to recognize emotions in others i.e Social Awareness and 4. the capacity to regulate emotions in others i.e Relationship Management . All these factors have a greater association with each other.

“**Emotional Self-Awareness and Expression**”, is the factor which concerns the skill with which individuals perceive, understand and express their own emotions. **Self-awareness** helps to recognize one’s own emotions and how they affect thoughts and behavior. One can assess his strengths and weaknesses and generate self-confidence. An awareness of his emotional state helps him plan his actions, think creatively, redirect his focus and motivate himself to get the best out of any situation. Emotional facilitation of thinking describes emotional sensations and asked to simulate situations where any specific emotion is predominant.

“**Emotional Self-Management**”, concerns the skill and capacity with which individual can effectively understand, regulate and manage their own emotions. Emotional understanding helps in recognizing two emotions blend and emotion progresses from one to other. It is about to diminish the longevity and impact of unpleasant emotions such as anger, frustration or anxiety and move through them swiftly and smoothly to cultivate pleasant and appropriate emotions such as feeling calm, appreciation and enthusiasm. It will enable one to control impulsive feelings and behaviour to overcome negative emotion in healthy ways and have wide range of choices over the emotions to adapt to changing circumstances at any given time. It is intrapersonal management of emotions, comprising of assertiveness and independence that inculcate the ability to be self-directed and self-controlled in one’s thinking and actions and to be free of emotional dependence.

“**Emotional Awareness**” of others” assesses the skill with which individuals perceive and understand the emotions of others. Most models and measures of EI comprise variables concerned with the capacity to perceive and understand the emotions of others. According to Goleman (2000a) this area of EI is ‘**Social Awareness**’, that is, the capacity to recognize emotions in others. It is the ability to be aware of, to understand and to appreciate the feelings of others”. It is meant to be empathetic enough to understand the emotions, needs and concerns of others, pick

up on emotional cues, feel comfortable socially and recognize and understand the power dynamics in a group or organization. **Social intelligence** helps in being empathetic enough to comprehend the purpose of interpersonal behavior and the role it plays in effective adaptability (Zirkel, 2000). This builds the capacity of the individual to act purposefully and therefore define human effectiveness from the social perspective.

Relationship management is regulating emotions to well engage with others. It is a process that begins with emotional awareness and one’s ability to recognize and understand what other people are experiencing. Once emotional awareness is in play, one can effectively develop additional social/emotional skills that will make one’s relationships more valuable, fruitful and fulfilling. By appraisal and regulation of emotion in self and others, a person will be able to accurately perceive and respond to his emotions accurately as well as he will be better in expressing it to others. At the same time, he would be able to value the emotions in others. This allows him to adapt to the situation and have better social skills. These skills are part of emotional intelligence as it requires the processing and organisation of emotional information in oneself and in others. Mayer and Salovey (1997) have concluded that the ability to express inner feelings and emotions is highly related on the capacity to perceive emotions of others.

Emotional Intelligence and Human Capital is the intangible assets and qualities that improve worker performance and benefit the economy. It is possessed by the people who receive or possess them. It is owned by the people not by the organizations. Organizations rent or hire it. By nurturing EI people may foster transformational approach to create a necessary socio-emotional nearness with people around him. The resultant strengthening of bonds between the individuals help both parties to establish trust and mutuality based on common interests, goals, and a sense of mission in creating the necessary conditions for achievement of personal and organizational goals. Essentially in the era of social networking to connect and be connected the individual has to bring into play certain personal, social and organizational competencies in mutually acceptable manner for achieving organizational excellence. This social connectivity is based on empathy, service and organizational awareness. It involves understanding behavior in interpersonal context. Interactivity empathy, service and organizational awareness are corner stone of social connectivity.

Emotional Competency helps the individual to focus on the current task in hand and try to do it with utmost

efficiency and accuracy. This will also involve the use of creative thoughts and innovative principles in handling the tasks more effectively. In a study by Lyons and Schneider (2005), it was found that emotional intelligence is correlated with more challenge and improved performance. Lopes et. al. (2006) found that employees with elevated emotional intelligence moved higher in rank and awarded greater merit increase than their counterparts. These employees also got better peer and/or supervisor ratings of interpersonal facilitation and stress management. A study by Jaeger (2003) revealed a strong relationship between emotional intelligence and performance of employees.

Sy, Tram and O'Hara (2006) reported managers' emotional intelligence had a stronger positive correlation with job satisfaction and job performance. Lyons and Schneider (2005) found that high emotional intelligence levels promote challenge appraisal and lead to better performance. According to Stein and Book (2006) the concept of self as the ability to recognize one's feelings and be able to differentiate between them and also understand what caused that feeling. Since emotional intelligence comprises both intra-personal and interpersonal abilities, the success of self is the key component of emotional intelligence.

Thus, emotionally intelligent behavior addresses the basic issues for fostering workplace effectiveness and supports to achieve higher levels of organizational growth and excellence. This essentially helps in developing and maintaining congenial work environment leading to efficiency at the workplace and development of human capital.

Organisations have started focusing on emotional competency dimensions of the human being that deals with those ultimate human capacities and potentialities, which have a significant impact on the various aspects of organizational climate and emotionally healthy workplace. Enrichment of the emotional dimension would help to solve behavioural problems arising from material and social dimensions and contribute to the true effectiveness of an organization (Elankumaran et.al, 2005). EI promote emotional stability and help in diversity management.

Organisation need technical knowledge as well as social and emotional abilities to augment customer delight. Emotional intelligence can contribute to developing those particular skills and abilities to fulfill the aspiration of meeting those objectives (Orme & Langhorn, 2003). Personal competencies play a very vital role in influencing the emotional intelligence of employees in organizations.

Hatfield, Cacioppo, and Rapson (1994) found that the ability to use and manage emotions to guide thinking can support an individual not only in understanding and comprehending emotions but also technical information in order to assess and resolve an interpersonal problem. In this study, EI dimensions like 'self-awareness' helps to consider the emotions of one's own emotions and 'self-management' helps to manage the technical information to the employees. There is a strong correlation between the 'self-awareness' 'self-management' and performance of the employees.

Law, Song, and Wong (2004) and Van Rooy and Viswesvaran (2004) in their findings suggested that emotionally intelligent persons are better performers in comparison to their counterparts. Jansen, Karina (2006) studied determinants of psychological wellbeing. The study extracted Interpersonal mastery consisting of Positive Affect, Emotional Management, Sense of Coherence, Life Satisfaction and Optimism and Intrapersonal mastery consisting of Emotions-Others, Emotions-Own, Happy Emotions and Non-Verbal Emotions contribute to psychological wellbeing. R.Krishnaveni and Deepa (2011) in their findings suggest Emotional Intelligence and better Performance Evaluation. EI moderates psychological stress, consider it as a challenge, contribute to mental psychosomatic, and physical health which is inevitable for individual and organisational performance (Choudhury, J.2020).

3. OBJECTIVES

- To study on the concept emotional intelligence and its components
- To discuss the association between emotional intelligence and emotionally intelligent behavior
- To study on the literature with emotional intelligence emotionally intelligent behavior and its impact on fostering Human Capital and Performance.

4. METHODOLOGY

The research work is conceptual in nature based on secondary data only. In this regard various research on Emotional Intelligence were studied and analyzed extensively. Study also explored the existing literature to analyses the relation between EI, Emotionally intelligent behavior, socio emotional competency, individual development and subsequent organization development.

5. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Table 2. Conceptual Framework of the Research: Source: Developed by Author

6. FINDINGS

Emotional intelligence bears an important impact on the self-development of an individual. People exhibit emotionally intelligent behavior that gains positive relations and emotional commitment of employees. At a higher level, emotional intelligence fortifies organizational culture, refine its resilience and stretches its flexibility and build emotionally healthy workplace. Managers who believe in emotional intelligence supervisory approach are highly concern for emotional drainage and burnout of employees and therefore, take the responsibilities to foster emotionally healthy workplace. They understand the importance of communication, collaboration, cooperation, interdependency and interconnectivity. Thereby, they develop an culture of treating each and every employee with dignity and respect. High levels of trait EI amplify the beneficial effects of active coping which is intra-psychic that helps an individual to manage external and internal demands and conflicts that results from stressful encounters in life which exceed his personal resources. People with high EI can influence their subordinates and peers to increase the level of EI as they nurture the ability and competencies to understand and control their own emotion and emotion of others. Thereby it encourages interpersonal relations, group cohesiveness and team work. People with high level of EI have emotional clarity, ability to repair emotion, emotion regulation and have high self-esteem. Therefore, an emotionally intelligent organization in which employees have strong connections among themselves as well as with employers can work more efficiently and increase productivity.

7. SUGGESTIONS

Much remains oblivious of regarding the concept EI (Matthews, Zeidner, & Roberts, 2007). But it is a promising area for study. Emotionally intelligent employers need to create emotionally intelligent workforce mix by hiring employees who exhibit a high emotional intelligence, by appraising employees by emotional intelligence criteria, by integrating emotional intelligence into performance management system and offering training to work on developing emotional competence. EI can be taught learnt. Knowledge on emotion enhances EI. One has to gain knowledge continuously to embed right thought in order to understand emotions and feelings that can nurture his own individual resilience and develop human capital. EI and resilience behaviour can be developed through support, training and education as well as management intervention for EI training. Therefore, the study suggests incorporation of emotion education at organisation level for psychological resilience-building and enhancement of self-efficacy. Organisation has to provide the appropriate environment and invest on training and education to learn more of emotional competency which subsequently provides the empathetic environment to reap the benefit of developing human capital. Because environment is the breeding place in which emotional intelligence, emotional competency, resilient behaviour takes birth and develop.

8. CONCLUSION

EI is a distinct form of intelligence for Emotional and Intellectual Growth. Cognitive skill helps to join in an organization but to sustain and succeed one need emotional. Emotional competency is a crucial resource for an individual for personal, professional and organizational

development. It contributes towards social cohesion for social and economic returns by adopting to or influencing others in accordance with demand of the situation. In the workplace, emotional intelligence is to be sensitive and perceptive of other's emotions which consumes the ability to intuitively improve performance based on this knowledge. As world of work demands an individual's cognitive, emotional and physical resources, promoting EI is increasingly important. It is observed and measured that Individuals with high emotional intelligence exhibit higher productivity. They learn better conflict resolution skill to adopt to or influence other's emotion to build strong bonds with co-workers as they can more easily understand the desires and needs of other people. Incorporating emotional intelligence in personal and organizational management philosophy may be the best way to maintain talent level which will help the organization not to experience resource crunch. Emotional intelligent people have the know-how to build and mature emotional capital as they consider it as personal bank account. They learn adoptive emotional functioning in understanding, utilizing and managing emotions in the own self and others to deal with interpersonal relationship thoughtfully and empathetically for emotional and intellectual growth. Yet, at workplaces emotions have very little place. It has always been put out of the door. But emotions are as important as intelligence as it shapes and conditions entire human life. It acts as a catalyzer to build human capital (knowledge, skill and ability). Proper human capital formation and development will not happen if appropriate emotional capital will go missing from human life. Emotional capital is a booster capital to accumulate and leverage human capital.

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